

MIXED-MODE FRACTURE ANALYSIS OF DELAMINATION USING NON-LINEAR EXTENDED FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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1 General Introduction

Fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials have received close attention over the past few decades due to their structural functionalities such as high strength to weight ratios, corrosion resistance and durability. However, their performance may still fade under complex failure mechanisms such as delamination which can be a result of excessive loading and interlaminar stress concentration. Commonly, the combined effects of normal and shear stress fields cause crack propagation in composite materials and it is essential to take into account such loading conditions in evaluating their fracture properties. The interlaminar delamination in FRP composites can also accompany other local material deformation/failure mechanisms such as fibre bridging and micro-cracking. Such mechanisms, in turn, can cause the process zone size in the crack front to be significantly larger than proposed lengths for brittle materials, and hence deviate from basic assumptions of the linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) [1]. Both experimental and numerical approaches have been employed in the past to study the mixed-mode failure of FRP materials. Here we briefly review these approaches.

In the case of experimental studies, for mixed-mode crack propagation the edge delamination tension (EDT) test was introduced in [2]. The EDT test specimen consists of a multidirectional lay-up and when it is loaded on its edge, the different effective elastic properties in different layers lead to combined normal and shear stresses in the layup interfaces and consequently the crack initiation begins in the specimen during loading. The asymmetric double cantilever beam (DCB) test was developed in [3]. This test has several benefits such

as simple specimen manufacturing and the testing procedure; however, it requires a complex loading unit. The mixed-mode flexural test proposed in [4] has a simple fixture similar to the three-point bending test. The major disadvantage of the mixed-mode flexural test is related to the requirement in manufacturing several specimens with different thicknesses of the loading arm to capture different ratios of mode mixities. The mixed-mode bending (MMB) test was developed by [5] with an idea to superimpose the mode I and mode II tests. The MMB test has demonstrated [5] robust characteristics in terms of the preparation of specimens, test procedure and different mode mixities study.

In the case of numerical studies of fracture tests, several models have been employed by researchers to regenerate different experimental fracture mechanics experimental datasets [6-29]. The virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) was proposed in [6] on the basis of the LEFM where a pre-assigned crack is inserted in the model and the crack tip plastic zone (process zone) is considered relatively small. The application of VCCT combined with the path independent contour integral methods (such as the J-integral) has proven to be an effective numerical tool in finding the fracture toughness values of materials. In the case of FRP composites and especially unidirectional laminates, the process zone is larger than the LEFM limit and it refuses the VCCT requirement of having an extricated crack tip. Cohesive zone model (CZM) is another approach that has drawn the attention of several researchers in modelling delamination in FRP composite materials [7]. CZM suites well with the large process zone occurring during the crack extension in such materials. The application of CZM requires

considering an embedded layer of CZM elements as the delamination path, which introduces the element size of embedded elements into the modelling as an important factor [8-9]. Another recent development in the application of FEM in modelling the fracture mechanics problem is the extended finite element method (XFEM) combined with the J-integral [10]. In XFEM, a crack surface is modelled into a regular FEM mesh without any need for re-meshing during damage progression. To enhance the ability of the XFEM in modelling discontinuities, a comprehensive framework capable of considering cohesive cracks and frictional contact was introduced in [11]. Later, cohesive cracks were modelled in concrete [12]. The example application of XFEM in composite materials was introduced in [13]. More recent investigations have also applied XFEM to model ‘mode-I’ delamination of unidirectional (UD) composites [14-15].

In the present work, the ‘mixed mode bending’ (MMB) fracture of an FRP composite is studied via a user-defined non-linear XFEM model in ABAQUS. The results are compared to experimental data in the literature and conclusions are derived on the performance of the XFEM model.

2 Mixed Mode Bending (MMB) Test

As mentioned earlier, the mixed-mode bending (MMB) test was first investigated and introduced in [5]. The test was developed to study mixed-mode fracture characteristics of materials with the idea of superposing mode I and mode II. The MMB test fixture contains a three-point bending test fixture with a loading arm which can be adjusted to wide range of mode mixities from pure mode I, similar to the double cantilever bending (DCB) test, to pure mode II, similar to the end-notched flexural (ENF) test. The specimen employed to perform the test is often formed with pre-inserted impenetrable Teflon as a crack in the mid-layer of laminate to represent the existing delamination in the sample. The test configuration is shown in Figure 1. One can decouple the MMB test into equivalent DCB and ENF tests to find the energy release rate for each mode. Implementing the standard beam theory, the following equations are extracted for mode I and II energy release rates [5]:

$$G_I = \frac{3\delta^2 E_{Long} h^3}{4a^4 \left(\frac{3c-L}{2L} \right)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{II} = \frac{9\delta^2 E_{Long} h^3 a^2}{(3a^4 + 0.5L^3)^2 \left(\frac{c+L}{2L} \right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where G_I , G_{II} , E_{Long} , δ , a , h , c and L are mode I and mode II fracture toughness values, longitudinal module of elasticity, deflection of the mid-hinge, crack length, half of the section thickness, arm of loading and the half of span length of the beam, respectively. Eqs. (1) and (2) are derived by the assumption that the lever arm of the loading hinge is positioned in the middle of the span. In this case, the mode mixity can vary by changing the location of loading point on the lever arm length, c .

3 Overview of the Non-linear Extended Finite Element Method

Conventional finite element method (FEM) has frequently demonstrated numerical difficulties such as elastic snap back, artificial softening and strong mesh dependency [27] when dealing with discontinuities, cracks and material interfaces. To tackle these burdens, the extended finite element method (XFEM) was proposed [10] where the partition of unity (PUM) concept [16] was utilized into FEM approximations. Over the last decade, the XFEM has started receiving accelerated attention among researchers, leading to advances and further improvements of the method. The study [17] implemented 3D XFEM in modeling discontinuities while [18] developed the friction surfaces on the crack. Studies [19-20] analyzed dynamic propagation of the crack and developed new singular enrichment functions. Later, the studies [21-24] extracted new static and dynamic enrichment functions for analysis of composite materials.

In XFEM, similar to conventional FEM, the finite element mesh is generated regardless of discontinuities locations. Then, specific search algorithms such as the level-set or fast marching methods [10] are utilized to identify the location of

any discontinuity with respect to the existing mesh and distinguish different types of required enrichments for the affected mesh elements. Next, additional auxiliary degrees of freedom are added to the conventional FEM approximations in selected nodes around the discontinuity. These degrees of freedom assist the model in capturing the displacement jumps caused by discontinuities. Assume a discontinuity (a crack) within an arbitrary finite element mesh. The displacement field of point x , $u^g(x)$, inside the material domain can be described in two parts; the conventional finite element approximation, and the XFEM enriched field defining the discontinuity [10]:

$$u^g(x) = \sum_I \phi_I(x) u_I^{ord} + \sum_J \phi_J(x) \psi(x) u_J^{enr} \quad (3)$$

where $\phi(x)$, $\psi(x)$, u^{ord} and u^{enr} are the conventional FEM shape function, the general enrichment function, the classic degrees of freedom at each node and the additional enriched degree of freedom. In the case of cohesive cracks, the study [11] was the first to apply the 1D sub-segment on the crack interface to include the cohesive traction in the cohesive region of the crack front. The study [12] implemented the XFEM in modeling the cohesive cracks in concrete material and studied the XFEM model in comparison to experimental tests. More recently, nonlinear 3D contact problems were [25] simulated by introducing a new XFEM formulation based on the summation of material and geometrical stiffness matrices. The enrichment function in displacement field can be defined as follow:

$$\psi_j^{enr} = \phi_j \left(\sum_k \phi_k H_k - H_j \right) \quad (4)$$

where H is the Heaviside step function. Introducing the Eq. (4) into Eq. (3), the proposed total tangential stiffness matrix, \bar{K}_T , was summarized as follows [25]:

$$\bar{K}_T = K_{Mat} + K_{Geo} = \int_{\Omega} \bar{B}^T D_S^{ep} \bar{B} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} G^T M_S G d\Omega \quad (5)$$

where K_{Mat} , K_{Geo} , \bar{B} , D_S^{ep} , G , M_S are the material stiffness, geometrical stiffness, strain gradient matrix, elasto-plastic constitutive matrix, Cartesian gradient matrix and the re-arranged second Piola-Kirchhoff, respectively.

In order to model the cohesive cracks, the study [12] proposed the application of the bilinear traction-separation law (Figure 2) to introduce a cohesive behaviour into the crack tip region by means of rearranging the nodal displacement components. They also implemented a transformation matrix (\bar{B}_{Coh}) to rearrange the nodal degree of freedoms and rewrite the crack opening ($v_{Opening}$) and sliding displacements ($v_{Sliding}$) and the surface traction T as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{Opening} & v_{Sliding} \end{bmatrix} = \bar{B}_{Coh} U \quad (6)$$

$$T = \bar{D}_{Interface} \bar{B}_{Coh} U \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{D}_{Interface}$ includes interface material properties and U contains the FE displacement degrees of freedom. In a more detailed format, Eq. (8) can be expanded as

$$\begin{cases} T = K_{Pen} v & v \leq v_0 \\ T = (1-D) K_{Pen} v & v_0 < v \leq v_f \\ T = 0 & v_f < v \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where the damage index, D , in a pure mode I/II test is a function of crack opening/sliding, v , critical crack opening/sliding, v_0 , and the failure crack opening/sliding, v_f ; K_{Pen} is the penalty stiffness. The damage index in a bilinear traction-separation law is defined as:

$$D = \frac{v_f}{v} \left(\frac{v - v_0}{v_f - v_0} \right) \quad (9)$$

Above mentioned relationships between the crack opening/sliding displacements and the interface material damage indices are valid when no interaction between fracture modes is expected. In a case where combined opening and sliding displacements are present, the assumption of

uncoupled damage indices for each mode may be unreliable. For instance, because of a large process zone at the crack front for mode I (normal opening), it is not expected to observe any stress singularity in this region. This assumption may be contradicted by mode II (tangential sliding) acting on the same plane as mode I and causes a stress concentration due to cohesive traction on the crack surface. To overcome this difficulty, the study [27] employed the concept of effective separation displacement, v_{eff} , and effective traction, σ_{eff} , as follows.

$$v_{eff} = \sqrt{v_{opening}^2 + \xi^2 v_{sliding}^2} \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{eff} = \sqrt{\sigma_{opening}^2 + \xi^2 \sigma_{sliding}^2} \quad (11)$$

where ξ is a dimensionless correction factor relating the crack sliding to the crack opening which may vary depending on the mode II participation in sample's failure (in the present work a value of 0.2 was considered for simulations). When modeling the mixed-mode fracture test, one can simply replace the displacement values in Eq. (9) with the effective separation displacement from Eq. (10). For modeling the contact between delamination faces, the static-dynamic friction law is employed to replace $\bar{D}_{Interface}$.

$$\bar{D}_{Interface} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{K}_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{K}_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{K}_{33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where \bar{K}_{11} is a large number to prevent the normal surface penetration (in the present work it was considered to be $10^3 \times E_{11}$). \bar{K}_{22} and \bar{K}_{33} were considered to be equal to shear modulus in static friction and 30% of shear modulus in dynamic friction. Finally, in order to include the cohesive interface material stiffness, the total tangential stiffness formulation, Eq. (5), can be redefined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{K}_T &= K_{Mat} + K_{Geo} + K_{Coh} = \\ &\int_{\Omega} \bar{B}^T D_S^{ep} \bar{B} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} G^T M_S G d\Omega + \\ &\int_{\Omega} (\bar{B}_{Coh})^T \bar{D}_{Interface} \bar{B}_{Coh} d\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

In order to extract the displacement field for presented nonlinear problem, the residual forces can be calculated using:

$$F_{int} = \int_{\Omega} \bar{B}^T \sigma d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \psi^{enrT} f^t d\Omega \quad (14)$$

Where, σ and f^t are the 2nd Piola-Kirchhoff tensor and the vector of traction forces on the crack surface.

4 Numerical Example

The numerical simulation of a UD laminate AS4-PEEK fiber reinforced composite (FRP) under MMB test was studied. The specimen dimensions are extracted from [28]. The specimen length ($2L$), width (w), thickness ($2h$) and initial crack length (a) are 150 mm, 25 mm, 3.12 mm and 50 mm, respectively (Fig. 3). Material mechanical and fracture properties are presented in Table 1. A MATLAB code in concert with ABAQUS was implemented to perform the XFEM simulations. In the first step, MATLAB code reads the nodal coordinates, connectivity tables, material mechanical properties, crack surface and fracture information. Using a level-set technique the MATLAB code recognizes the ordinary elements and enriched elements of the given model. It then assembles the input file for ABAQUS execution. ABAQUS utilizes the developed user element subroutine to run the model and writes the stress, strain and displacement fields in a result file. At this stage, MATLAB code reads these fields from the results file and calculates the energy release rate using the J-integral to evaluate the stability of the delamination. If the energy release rate is greater than the critical fracture toughness, the delamination is extended by the size of the cohesive zone length. Otherwise, the configuration remains unchanged and the lever arm is pulled further away. If the delamination is unstable, MATLAB re-writes the

new input file with extended delamination, otherwise it increases the grip opening displacement.

With the lever length to half-span length ratios of 0.3, 0.5 and 0.8, the experimental results in [28] were compared with XFEM numerical simulations. In Addition, different penalty stiffness values were employed in simulations to investigate the effect of this modeling variable in the XFEM accuracy. The comparison between experimental data and XFEM simulations in Fig. 4 shows agreeable trends of force-displacement curves. While in experimental data no softening was observed during the material degradation, in the XFEM model, the delamination starts gradually and leads to a softening behaviour. Such difference between experimental and numerical models may be reduced by using lower loading rates in experiments to avoid a sudden loss of specimen integrity. A 0.5 mm/min rate was used in experimental tests in [28] while a 0.05 mm/step was used in the XFEM numerical simulations (total of 120 steps).

In terms of model sensitivity to the penalty stiffness factor, it is evident from Fig. 5 that the nonlinear XFEM is not dependent on the penalty stiffness in the tested range of $10^3 - 10^5$ N/mm³. An analytical solution [29] of the problem has also been added in Fig. 5. After the on-set of crack propagation at the global opening displacement of about 3mm, recording of experimental data has been stopped while the analytical model and numerical simulation undertaking a softening region.

5 Conclusions

In this article, the application of the extended finite element method (XFEM) toward modeling the mixed-mode bending (MMB) test was presented. Nonlinear approximation was employed to increase the precision of numerical model while the contact surface and cohesive zone models were adapted into the code by means of rearranging the nodal displacement values. Simulation results were compared with analytical values and experimental data [28] in a MMB test on a UD laminate with different lever length to half-span length ratios. A similar trend between different modeling approaches was observed. In particular, the maximum force capacity of the specimen seems very close in all the

tested cases. With small loading increments, a gradual material softening in numerical results were observed, which differs from the sudden loss of material global stiffness seen from experimental data. Effect of different penalty stiffness factors was also studied and it was concluded that the XFEM model was not influenced by changes in the penalty stiffness. Future work in this area may include the effect of the mesh size and cohesive zone model traction-separation law to improve the accuracy of the numerical model. Also the validity of the effective separation displacement approach for an equivalent fracture formulation may be investigated further.

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Table 1. Elastic and fracture properties of the CFRP material modeled [28]

Elastic Properties	Fracture Properties
$E_{11} = 138 \text{ GPa}$	$T_{I\max} = 75.4 \text{ MPa}$
$E_{22} = E_{33} = 10.5 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{IC} = 980 \text{ mJ/m}^2$
$G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.3 \text{ GPa}$	$T_{II\max} = 96.3 \text{ MPa}$
$G_{23} = 3.5 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{IIC} = 1625 \text{ mJ/m}^2$
$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3$	
$\nu_{23} = 0.48$	

Figure 1. (a) Mixed mode bending (MMB) test fixture; (b) test specimen geometry

Figure 2. Bilinear traction-separation law for a cohesive delamination interface

Figure 3. XFEM model of the MMB test in ABAQUS.

Figure 5. Comparison between experimental data, analytical mode, and XFEM results of the MMB test with different penalty stiffness factors (mode mixity = 50%)

Figure 4. Comparison between experimental and XFEM results of the MMB test for different mode mixities